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SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE OF THE WORK

After having prepared the 6 oxygen carriers presented in the Deliverable D1.1, in this deliverable we present their basic characterization to select suitable materials to be tested in the project.

Before going into deep in the characterization aspects we have to remember which are the characteristics that can grant the oxygen carrier has a good performance (according to [1]):

- Oxygen transport capacity;
- Reactivity with fuel gases;
- Low Cost;
- Small coke deposition;
- Small tendency to agglomeration;
- Mechanical strength and resistance to attrition.

Among the above cited parameters the most important characteristics for the initial screening of oxygen carrier materials are the Oxygen Transport Capacity (R_{OC}), the reactivity and the mechanical strength.

The oxygen transport capacity is defined as in the following equation [2]:

$$R_{OC} = (m_o - m_r) / m_o \quad (1)$$

where m_o is the oxidized mass and m_r is the reduced mass. This parameter indicates the amount of oxygen which can be transferred by the oxygen carrier between the air reactor and the fuel reactor. It is a design parameter and influences the solids circulation rate between both reactors. We have to remember that for the oxygen transport capacity we have a theoretical value and an experimental one, which may be different. The theoretical value is calculated by determining the metal oxide content in the material by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES). The experimental oxygen transport capacity is determined through TGA experiments.

TGA tests are also used to determine the reactivity of the oxygen carrier materials with different fuel gases, e.g. CH₄, CO or H₂. The reactivity affects to the solids inventory of the two reactors. Here, reactivity is evaluated through the Rate Index (%/min), which is calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Rate Index (\%/min)} = 100 \cdot 60 \cdot \text{dm}_{\text{OC}}/\text{dt} \quad (2)$$

The mechanical strength of the particles is measured by determining the force applied to break the oxygen carrier particle.

In addition, other physic-chemical properties are determined to have a overall overview of the particles performance, namely mean particle size, density, porosity, specific surface area, crystalline phases.

SECTION 2: CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

The techniques followed for the oxygen carrier characterization are the same used in [3]. Different techniques were used to physically and chemically characterize the samples presented in deliverable d1.1:

- The total Fe₂O₃ content was determined by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) with a Jobin Yvon 2000 spectrometer.

- The experimental oxygen transport capacity, R_{OC}, and the reactivity were determined in a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), CI Electronics type. The reactor consisted of a quartz tube (24 mm i.d.) placed in an oven which can be operated at temperatures up to 1100 °C. The sample-holder

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was a wire mesh platinum basket (14 mm diameter and 8 mm height) to reduce mass transfer resistance around the solid sample. The flow rate of the reacting gas mixture (25 nL/h) was controlled by electronic mass flow controllers. In this project, reactivity with CH₄ at 950 °C will be determined for comparison purposes.

- A Shimpo FGN-5X apparatus was used to measure the crushing strength (C.S.) of particles as the force needed to fracture them. Crushing strength was obtained as the average value of at least 20 measurements for particles with a particle size range of $d_p = +100\text{--}300 \mu\text{m}$.

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- The mean particle size was measured by means of size particle distribution, via laser diffraction technique, according to the ISO 13320 Standard with LS 13 320 Beckman Coulter equipment.

- The skeletal density (ρ_s) of the particles was determined with a Micromeritics Model AccuPyc II 1340 helium pycnometer.

- Porosity (ϵ_p) was measured by Hg intrusion in a Quantachrome PoreMaster 33;

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-The specific surface (S_{BET}) was determined by the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method by adsorption/desorption of nitrogen at 77 K in a Micromeritics ASAP-2020 (Micromeritics Instruments Inc.).

- Crystalline chemical species were identified by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) in a Bruker AXS D8 Advance system, with Bragg–Brentano geometry configuration, Cu Ka radiation and equipped with secondary graphite monochromator.

SECTION 3: CHARACTERIZATION OF THE PREPARED OXYGEN CARRIER MATERIALS

Table 1 shows the main properties of the 6 materials selected as suitable oxygen carriers to be used in this project. It may be differentiated synthetic materials ($\text{Fe}_{20\gamma}\text{Al}$, $\text{Ni}_{18\alpha}\text{Al}$, $\text{Mn}_{66}\text{Fe}-7\text{Ti}$ and MnTi) and natural materials (ilmenite and Tierga Fe-ore).

Table 1: Main characteristics of the oxygen carrier samples prepared and characterized at the Instituto de Carboquimica.

	$\text{Fe}_{20\gamma}\text{Al}$	$\text{Ni}_{18\alpha}\text{Al}$	$\text{Mn}_{66}\text{Fe}-\text{Ti}7$	$\text{Mn}-\text{Ti}20$	Ilmenite	Fe-ore
Metal oxide content (wt.%)	20	18	100	93	80	76.5
XRD	Fe_2O_3 $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	NiO NiAl_2O_4 $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	$(\text{Mn}_{0.66}\text{Fe}_{0.34})_2\text{O}_3$ $(\text{Mn}_{0.66}\text{Fe}_{0.34})_3\text{O}_4$ TiO_2	Mn_3O_4 Mn_2TiO_4	Fe_2TiO_5 Fe_2O_3 TiO_2	Fe_2O_3 SiO_2 CaO MgO
$\text{R}_{\text{OC,theor}}$ (%)	2.0	3.8	9.5	6.2	4.0	2.5
$\text{R}_{\text{OC,exp}}$ (%)	1.6	<3.8	9.5	4.7	3.3	2.5
Rate index, CH_4 (%/min)	8.8	25.9	4.5	2.3	0.6	2.0
ρ_s (kg/m^3)	3950	2500	4940	4850	4100	4210
C.S. (N)	1.5	4.1	1.9	3.7	3.8	5.8
ε_p (%)	50.5	42.5	30.0	20.0	1.2	26.3
S_{BET} (m^2/g)	39.1	7.0	<1	<1	<1	1.4

$\text{Fe}_{20\gamma}\text{Al}$

The $\text{Fe}_{20\gamma}\text{Al}$ material was prepared by incipient wet impregnation on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, being 20 wt.% Fe_2O_3 after the calcination process. During the thermal treatment, $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ was converted into $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. The theoretical oxygen transport capacity is 2.0 wt.%, considering that Fe_2O_3 may be reduced to FeAl_2O_4 in the presence of Al_2O_3 . However, the formation of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ caused a partial deactivation of the support, limiting the extension of the reduction to Fe_3O_4 in a fraction of the iron oxide. This, the experimental oxygen transport capacity was 1.6 wt.%. The reactivity with CH_4 was relatively high (Rate index=8.8 %/min). On the contrary, the crushing strength was low due to the alumina transformation.

$\text{Ni}_{18\alpha}\text{Al}$

The system $\text{NiO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ has been proved to be suitable for preparation of OC [4-16]. However, it is well known that the preparation method and the

nature of the support influence the stability and activity of the nickel catalysts [17]. The metallic dispersion and the metal–support interaction are the most important characteristics of a nickel catalyst. Similar results were found for nickel-based OC. Mattison et al. [8] found that the Ni spinel (NiAl_2O_4) was present when using high calcination temperatures ($T > 800$ °C) due to the solid–solid reaction of NiO with Al_2O_3 . This aluminate can react with methane in the reduction reaction of the OC, but the thermodynamic of this reaction shows a low methane conversion to $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at temperatures typical for the CLC process (gas conversion 6–95%, $T > 900$ °C). However, the conversion of methane for free NiO is always higher than 98% at these temperatures. In a previous work [18] the effect of the support on the reactivity and selectivity during methane combustion of impregnated NiO– Al_2O_3 OC was examined, using thermal and chemical modifications of the support. The OC prepared by incipient wet impregnation on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ had low reduction reactivity and low selectivity to CO_2 and H_2O due to the strong interaction between the NiO and the alumina to form the NiAl_2O_4 compound.

Therefore, it was decided to prepare the Ni-based material by incipient wet impregnation directly on $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. The OC prepared using $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ had much better performance for the combustion of methane due to the weak interaction of the NiO with this thermally modified alumina. Therefore, it seems that an adequate Ni–Al OC for the CLC process should have the biggest fraction of the Ni introduced as free NiO phase instead of as the spinel form. Nevertheless, it was observed that a fraction of NiO interacted with alumina support after the oxidation step. The amount of NiO forming nickel aluminate depended on the variation of the oxygen carrier conversion during the redox cycles. As a consequence, the oxygen transport capacity may be lower than the theoretical value of 3.8 wt.%.

The Ni-based oxygen carrier was highly reactive with CH_4 , showing a Rate index value of 25.9 %/min. In addition, the use of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ as a raw material reduced the chemical stress during the calcining process, allowing the achievement of particles with high values of the crushing strength.

Mn66Fe-Ti7

A synthetic oxygen carrier, named Mn66Fe-Ti7, based on manganese and iron oxides with TiO_2 addition was prepared by spray granulation in a

spouted bed reactor at the ICB-CSIC using 60 wt% of Mn₃O₄ (Elkem), 33 wt% of Fe₂O₃ (Chemlab) and a 7 wt% of TiO₂ (Panreac) [19]. The name given reflects the atomic Mn/Fe ratio (Mn/Fe = 66/34) in the mixture and the weight percentage of TiO₂ in it (7%). Both parameters were included in the name given to this material since its chemical and mechanical properties are conditioned by them. The oxygen carrier was calcined in air atmosphere during 2 h at 1050 °C. After that, the particles were sieved and a final particle size distribution between 0.1 and 0.3 mm was considered. The stoichiometric formula of the particles was (Mn_{0.66}Fe_{0.34})₂O₃·(TiO₂)_{0.15}.

The MnFe mixed oxide shows a high oxygen transport capacity, while the reactivity with CH₄ was moderate. Interestingly, this material showed magnetic properties due to the existence of the spinel phase, as well as oxygen uncoupling capability; i.e., molecular O₂ is released under the existing operating conditions. These properties make that this material was more suitable for the combustion of solids fuels.

Mn-Ti20

A MnTi mixed oxide was prepared by mechanical mixing of precursor powders: Mn₃O₄ (Micromax ®, ELKEM) and TiO₂ (Panreac Prs). The different proportions of the raw materials were mixed in a ball mill for 30 min. Then, the mixtures were pelletized by pressure in a hydraulic press at 165 bar during 60 s. Cylindrical pellets were so obtained of about 1 cm in diameter and 3 cm in length. These pellets were calcined in a muffle in air at 1030 °C during 2 h in order to achieve a material with high enough mechanical strength. After calcination, the pellets were crushed and sieved to the desired size (100–300 µm) [20].

The MnTi oxygen carrier showed improved characteristics compared to Mn-based materials without Ti addition. However, the rate index with CH₄ was relatively low, which makes this material was not optimal to be used in the present project.

Ilmenite

Ilmenite was first proposed as an oxygen carrier in the paper of Leion et al [21]. It is a mineral composed by iron and titanium [22, 23] with the chemical formula FeTiO₃. In reality, ilmenite is contained in some natural

iron ores which are also called ilmenite even though they contain together with the mineral also other compounds. In this work, a Norwegian ilmenite was used. Mineral rocks were crushed, sieved to 100-300 μm and calcined at 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h. After calcination, the material was mainly composed by Fe_2TiO_5 and Fe_2O_3 , with some TiO_2 and other inerts. The oxygen transport capacity corresponded to the reduction to FeTiO_3 and Fe_3O_4 . The oxygen transport capacity (3.3 wt.%) was lower than the theoretical value (4 wt.%) due to the presence of Fe_2O_3 . Ilmenite particles have a relatively high crushing strength value, but the reactivity with CH_4 was quite low.

Tierga iron-ore

Tierga ore is a mineral from a hematite mine in Tierga (Zaragoza, Spain) [24]. It has been crushed in ICB laboratories to the dimensions of +100–300 μm . Compared to ilmenite, Tierga Fe-ore shows lower oxygen transport capacity, as the redox system $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ has a lower fraction of oxygen being transferred than the $\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5/\text{FeTiO}_3$ system. However, its reactivity was higher. Nevertheless, the reactivity with CH_4 was low to be considered a suitable oxygen carrier in this project.

SECTION 4: PRIORITIZATION OF THE EVALUATED MATERIALS

Taking into account the characterization of the materials considered in the initial portfolio of oxygen carriers, a prioritization may be done on the basis of their main properties, such as oxygen transport capacity, reactivity and crushing strength. Thus, the preference to follow in the selection of materials is:

1. $\text{Ni}_{18}\alpha\text{Al}$: this synthetic material shows the highest reactivity, as well as a high crushing strength value. Although there are materials with a higher oxygen transport capacity, its value is suitable to be used in a CLC system.
2. $\text{Fe}_{20}\gamma\text{Al}$: its relatively high reactivity with CH_4 makes that this synthetic material was also a preferred material to be used in the project.

3. Mn₆₆Fe-Ti₇: this synthetic material, prepared from cheap metals, has a high oxygen transport capacity. The lower reactivity with CH₄ makes that this oxygen carrier was considered as the third option.
4. Tierga Fe-ore: this is a natural ore with a relatively high reactivity with CH₄. However, it can be anticipated that it will not be enough to achieve high conversions of CH₄.
5. Ilmenite: this material shows a quite low reactivity with CH₄. Although it could be increased during its operation in a CLC unit, there is a high degree of uncertainty about its activation under the high temperature conditions that will be used in this project.
6. Mn-Ti₂₀: compared to ilmenite, this material showed a higher reactivity with CH₄. However, it is desired that a synthetic material was able to fully convert CH₄ in a CLC unit, which would not be the case.

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